

EFFECT OF REGULATORY ACCOUNTING POLICIES ON THE FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT OF ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION COMPANIES (DisCos) IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examines the effect of regulatory accounting policies (RAP) on the financial management (FM) of electricity distribution companies DisCos in Nigeria. Data was collected from primary source and a structured questionnaire was used to elicit information from financial officers of the 11 DisCos in Nigeria. A multiple regression analysis was adopted, and the data was analysed using the partial least square Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) technique. The findings of the study revealed that RAP have a significant effect on the FM of DisCos in Nigeria. The study recommends that the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) further strengthen its regulatory oversight by enforcing the adaption of the uniform system of accounts USofA, applying and imposing sanctions where necessary for non-compliance as well as incentives such as timely review of OPEX requests to encourage continuous compliance and improvement by the DisCos.

Keywords: Regulatory Accounting Policies, Asset Management, Capital Budget Management, Working Capital Management, Financial Management, DisCos.

1. INTRODUCTION

Regulatory accounting policy requirements may pose certain threat to the transparency required in a financial report. This may also have some implications on the financial management system of an organization as too flexible accounting policy choices provide opportunity for fiendish accountants to act thoughtlessly towards the transparency required of the financial management system. United States Agency for International Development (2019) listed accounting as one of the key areas requiring attention in the electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in their report on Nigeria Power Sector Program (NPSP). The report further noted the financial management and accounting system were undergoing decentralization process which may require some regulatory inputs to enable them to attain some regulatory benefits from the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC).

In a bid to standardised accounting practice and generate consistent regulatory accounting reports for all regulated entities in the Nigerian Electricity Industry (NESI), NERC developed a uniform system of accounts (USofA). The USofA is expected to serve as a basis for evaluating the performance and financial health of the entities which is crucial in tariff setting and ensuring a sustainable and competitive electricity system. It requires the accounting separation of regulated and non-regulated activities, while facilitating the preparation of financial statements in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). The NERC as a

regulator, conducts selected audits and reviews to assess licensee compliance with the policy document. (USofA, 2014).

Academic studies on accounting policies have often concentrated on professional accounting policies, particularly in the aspects of the adoption of international financial reporting standards. Rossouw (2010) Examined public sector accounting policies in situations of choice while, Cernius & Birskyte (2020), Efeeloo, et.al (2021), Odo and Isamade (2021), Erhan and Gamureac (2022) examined accounting policies concentrating on specific standards like International Public Sector Accounting Standard (IPSAS). These studies have largely ignored the possible effect of regulatory accounting policies in financial management at the instance of dynamic and changing accounting policies. Hence the need to examine how financial management of electricity distribution companies (DisCos) has been affected by regulatory accounting policies.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Policies and Accounting Policies

The central concern of policies is usually with respect to actors and their interactions (Howlett et al, 2024). Policy occurs at different levels of human interaction such as public, organizational and personal (Maruszewska et al., 2023). Historically, word policy was derived from a combination of Greek, Sanskrit and Latin languages (Dunn, 2004). Policy is a predetermined course of action, which is established to provide a guide toward accepted business strategies and objectives (Manghani, 2011) therefore providing a direct link between an organization's vision and its day-to-day operations. Policies identify the key activities and provide a general course of action to decision-makers on how to handle issues as they arise and provide a uniform approach to recurring matters. Policy has hardly been explained with a standard definition as it is assumed not to have a simple, generally acceptable definition (Torjman, 2005). It could be perceived as a process that transforms ideas and principles into practice rather than just a discrete entity that is considered as the output of a political system (Word et al, 2016).

According to Sapru (2012), policy signifies guidance for actions and assumes the form of a declaration of goals, a general purpose and an authoritative action. Vickers (1965) defines policy as decisions that give directions, coherence, and continuity to the course of action for which the decision-making body is accountable. Policy is a purposed course of action of a person, group or the government within a given environment, providing obstacles and opportunities which the policy was proposed to utilize and overcome in an effort to reach a goal or realize an objective or a purpose (Carl, 1967).

Meanwhile, policies are not mere codification of instructions. They involve a deliberate process of transforming ideas into guided actions having the target of attaining a specific goal in mind. Policies are purposefully streamlined as a course of action, codified and provided with requisite authoritative support to ensure the attainment of the intended objectives. Further to this, policies are either contrived by government to achieve a specific public objective or private sector oriented for an intended purpose. With respect to public sector policy, Olaniyi (1998)

considered it as a set of decisions taken by a political actor or group concerning the selection of goals and the method of attaining them, relating to a specified situation. Policies in the private sector typically outlines the role, rules and procedure by creating a framework within which the administration and staff can perform the assigned duties (Mayer & Thompson, 1982) thereby making it a plan of action agreed to by group of people with the power to carry it out and enforce it (Devon & Herbert-Boyd, 2000).

Policy is a declaration that defines the intention of a community, organization or government goals and priorities (Aiyede, 2022). Harrop (1992) intimate that policy involves “a buddle of decisions and how they are put into practice.” Policy is “A purposive course of action which has to be followed by a particular group/actor to address a particular problem or matter of concern (Anderson 1975).” Hence policies are not basically mere codification of principles but involves the enforcement and actualization of such principles. Simply put, a policy is a statement of the goals and objectives of an organization in relation to a particular subject and the description of the strategies by which the goals and objectives are to be achieved (Manjo, 2021).

2.2 Regulatory accounting Policy

In an effort to place Nigeria’s financial reporting practices on the same footing with global best practices, the “FRCN Act” was enacted. Osaynade (2022) noted that the “council will require management assessment of internal controls, including information systems controls with independent attestation” (p. 25). He stated further that the oversight of professionals, “involves a good code of ethics for financial reporting officers as certification of financial reports by chief finance officer and their chief executive officers so as to enable seamless formulation of accounting policies of reporting entities (Osayande, 2022). Furthermore, the council will consolidate efforts in mending the public perception of the financial reporting process since it issues code of corporate governance and develop a program for periodic assessment of new rules (Osayande, 2012). The enactment of the FRCN act according to Anao (2012), is considered timely as “it expands the scope of financial regulation beyond traditional spheres of accounting and financial reporting and also spans auditing and corporate governance” (p. 5). The increased involvement of government in financial reporting presents a picture that is ardently passionate about the public interest. Perhaps, because of the plethora of bank fraud exposures recorded in recent times in Nigeria and the urgent need to align with international best practices.

The regulatory affairs of a country are most times regulated by the national government who formulates policies to impose controls and restrictions on activities of country. These policies are not uniform because of the peculiarity of the industries as such different policies are formulated for each industry (Chu, 2016). In Nigeria, the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) is the primary legislation governing the formulation and management of companies which affects all residents and foreigners intending to or doing business in Nigeria. It is geared towards supporting the government initiative to improve ease of doing business in the country (CAMA, 2020).

With specific reference to accounting regulation, the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) of Nigeria, issues guidelines to regulate the financial operations of all quoted companies and other companies to a large extent. The Financial Reporting Council (FRC) of Nigeria is a regulatory body established by the Nigerian government to oversee financial reporting, corporate governance, and the audit profession in the country. It was established through the enactment of the Financial Reporting Council (FRC) of Nigeria Act in 2011. The FRC replaced the former Nigerian Accounting Standard Board (NASB) and also took on additional responsibilities related to corporate governance and regulation of the audit profession (Otoyebi, 2023). This is necessary to maintain consistency and uniformity as well as standard for decision-making in the industry.

Meanwhile, the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), being the regulator of the electricity supply industry (NESI), has come up with an accounting policy document titled “Uniform System of Accounts (USoA). The document aims to guide and regulate the activities of the industry by providing basic account descriptions, instructions, and accounting definitions for regulatory accounting reporting purposes by licensees in the electricity supply industry (NESI). It establishes a uniform format and set of accounting records that licensees are required to submit for regulatory purposes. Such records assist in providing an adequate information base for establishing tariffs and monitoring licensees’ performance. The goal is to make available accounting information that will enhance the efficiency and transparency of the regulatory process (UsofA, 2014).

The USofA requires the accounting separation of regulated and non-regulated activities while facilitating the preparation of financial statements in accordance with International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS). In certain instances, regulatory accounting records prepared in accordance with the USoA may differ from those required for statutory accounting purposes; in such cases, appropriate adjustments are required when preparing statutory financial statements. The NERC as a regulator, conducts selected audits and reviews to assess licensee compliance with the USofA (USofA, 2014).

The policy document therefore holds specifically for the regulation of the accounts of the distribution companies for specific accounting transactions. These transactions range from fixed assets classification as well as other transactions peculiar to the electricity distribution companies (DisCos). More specifically, it requires that all licensees shall prepare the regulatory accounting reports under the historical cost convention, regulations of the Commission, and other relevant provisions of CAMA. Where there is an inconsistency between the principles and these regulations, the treatment of items in the regulatory accounting reports shall be done in accordance with these regulations.

3. CONCEPT OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT

Financial management also referred to as business or corporate finance is the bedrock of all businesses. It refers to applying management concepts to budgeting, forecasting, managing, and controlling a company’s financial resources to achieve its stated objective. It aims to

maximize investors' profit by optimizing the company's money usage as well as deals with all the areas connected to profitability, expenses, cash, and credit (Ahmed, 2018).

According to Kirty Pandey (2017), financial management refers to that part of the management activity, which is concerned with planning and controlling a company's financial resources. Guthmann and Dougall (1962) define business finance as "the activity concerned with the planning, raising, controlling and administering the funds used in the business". Joseph Massie (1986) also describes financial management as "the operational activity of a business that is responsible for obtaining and effectively utilizing the funds necessary for efficient operations". Corporate finance, managerial finance and business finance are all terms used interchangeably to denote financial management. The fundamental goal of financial management is clearly to organize financial resources and thus increase the wealth of the company.

A company may go awry and incur losses without sound financial management. Financial management assists in estimating the short-term and long-term financial requirements of the business by effectively developing a present and future financial plan model, deciding the capital structure that is, the proportion of short-term and long-term funds, selection of the source of finance whether it is going to be debenture, share capital, or financial deposit, selection of the pattern of investment, proper cash management, implementations of financial controls, etc (Pandye, 2016).

3.1 Financial Management in Electricity Distribution Companies in Nigeria

The electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria play a pivotal role in providing essential services to industries and households, therefore, the effectiveness of their financial management is paramount for sustainable operations, growth and the overall stability of the Nigerian Electricity Supply Industry (NESI). According to Business Day (2020), the major bottleneck in the value chain of NESI is the distribution companies (DisCos). The crisis in the NESI is characterized by the recent takeover of many electricity distribution companies (DisCos) by commercial banks and lenders due to poor management performance, exemplified by loan default, the frequent collapse of the national electricity grid network, strike actions by electricity sector workers; and 44.6% of Nigerians still without access to the electricity grid-one of the highest in the world, in nominal terms (Uwanaka, 2022). Six out of the 11 DisCos have been taken over by Banks due to poor financial performance and management.

According to NESI stakeholders financing associated costing structure and poor management are the major challenges in the NESI. For many, the companies that bought majority stakes in many DisCos during the 2013 privatization lacked the financial capacity to deliver on the plans and goals expected of the DisCos (Uwanaka, 2022).

The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) in May 2023 cancelled the license of Kaduna Electricity Distribution Company (KAEDC) due to its prevailing financial and operation struggles stemming primarily from its massive debt, estimated at N110 billion (Sunday, 2023). Subsequently, in January 2024, NERC dissolved and reconstituted a new board. The dissolution of the board of KAEDC is a lesson to other DisCos because it highlights a critical need for other Discos to enhance their financial management, through efficient

revenue collection, minimizing technical losses, and adhering to investment commitments. There is also a need to have a robust investment strategy along with clear plans for long-term financial sustainability that can attract new investors and avoid being vulnerable (Ibrahim, 2023). Another notable issue that led to the dissolution was the lack of transparency and accountability in their financial dealings which led to a loss in public trust and confidence. Also, operational inefficiencies such as high technical losses and inadequate infrastructure were major obstacles in the DisCo (Nnodim, 2024). It will be of utmost importance to DisCos to upgrade their infrastructure, adopt and embrace new technologies, and review their operational process in a bid to supply reliable and cost-effective electricity (Akolo, 2023).

The DisCos can improve their financial management by adopting sustainable debt financing strategies to avoid excessive dependence on short-term loans and high interest rates as well as diversify funding sources (Pandey & Sahu, 2019; Ahmad & Ejaz, 2019; Kose et.al., 2020; Mazikana, 2021). Secondly, they can adopt cost-reduction initiatives across all operations, including procurement, maintenance, and staffing, and also invest in technology and automation to improve efficiency and reduce operational expenses (Agu et.al., 2024). Thirdly, Discos should invest in improved metering infrastructure and should endeavor to improve metering efficiency and accuracy to reduce revenue losses from meter tampering and under-billing. Discos should also implement robust revenue collection strategies to ensure timely payments from customers (ArunKumar et.al., 2024). Fourthly, DisCos should aim to maintain transparent and accurate financial records and ensure timely audits by independent bodies while implementing a strong internal control system to prevent fraud and mismanagement (Ziorklui et.al., 2024). Fifthly, there is a need for DisCos to strengthen their corporate governance practices by adopting international best practices and complying with relevant Nigerian laws, by that way creating transparent and reliable management (Lawuyi, 2022). Finally, Discos should always ensure strict compliance with all applicable regulations and policies governing the electricity sector, and regularly review and update internal procedures to ensure adherence to evolving regulatory requirements (Agu et.al., 2024).

4. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

The study of Okolie and Omoregie (2014) examined the uniformity and comparability of accounting policies of quoted companies in Nigeria. The objective is strictly restricted to the uniformity of accounting policy and the design employed in data collection is a cross-sectional survey of the accounting policies of 12 companies listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE). The study tested four critical areas of financial reports of companies including quality, presentation, disclosure and content of financial statements of the sampled companies. The results achieved by applying the chi-square statistic using U.M.P. invariant test, suggest that accounting policies are uniform in the form, types of numbers presented, the layout or format and management of accounting policies. However, their accounting practices are not uniform in the areas of quality, disclosure and content of financial statements and hence, their overall accounting practices. It is submitted that similar nomenclatures should be adopted in the accounting policies and financial statements preparations of all listed companies in NSE in order to increase uniformity, understandability and comparability of financial reports of

companies in Nigeria. In the study of Nangih et al., (2021), the influence of management's choice of accounting policy and accounting approximations in financial statements was directly examined on the quality of financial reports of Small and Medium Enterprises in Nigeria. The study was anchored on the Stakeholders' theory. The study also adopted the survey design approach. Data were mainly collected through the questionnaire and were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression techniques. Findings revealed that wrong accounting policies and judgements might affect the quality of financial reports, together with other factors. It was recommended that small and medium enterprise management adheres to accounting standards when designing their accounting policies and in their judgements/approximations to reduce material errors and enhance the quality of their financial report. Although this study seems related to the nexus between management and accounting policy choice, it precludes financial management and dwells principally on the private sector and the SMEs. The study also does not consider the possibility of various accounting policies that could probably affect financial management.

Rossouw (2010) identified 16 such accounting policy choices and presents the descriptive empirical results on which accounting policies were in fact chosen by a sample of 157 South African listed companies, in cases where IFRSs allow a choice between alternative accounting policies. Disclosure of accounting policies is necessary for the users of financial statements to enable them to compare the financial statements of various entities in making economic decisions. The research also found a lack of disclosures relating to chosen accounting policies in limited cases. Nevertheless, the study was unable to disaggregate accounting policy choices hence the need for specific research.

While the work of Raicevic and Stojilkovic (2022) establishes the importance of choosing and applying accounting policies in the corporate management system in the Republic of Serbia. The purpose of the study is to emphasize the value of selection and consistency in the application of appropriate accounting policies without primarily alluding to professional or government accounting policies. The purpose is therefore primarily on reliability and high-quality financial reporting. The variables used in the study include the share of a certain position in the total structure of assets, liabilities, income or expenses, characteristics of the chosen method, and observed period. Collection of primary data was carried out using the survey method, through a questionnaire technique, which was sent by mail. The questionnaire was sent to 120 company addresses in the Republic of Serbia. The answer came from 49 companies, which represent the sample on which this analysis was made. For the purposes of statistical analysis, SPSS software was used. The chosen accounting policies have a significant impact on the accuracy of financial statements. The attainment of the company's goals, which are represented in the achievement of the highest profit as well as the preservation of liquidity and the continuity of operations, is aided by decisions that are in line with the business policy of the company. Olatunji (2013) examined the impact of sound accounting systems on corporate performance of small and medium scale enterprises. This was done by a survey carried out through a questionnaire and analysed using the F-Statistic (ANOVA). Results showed that the adoption of a sound accounting system enhances the performance of small and medium scale businesses. It was recommended that accounting professionals should customize

accounting systems and audits to the need and capacities of these categories of businesses, provide accountancy services or a fee, and adherence of small business operators to internal controls. Badulescu et.al., (2021) assessed the determinants for the formulation of accounting practices and their impact on firm performance in Pakistan through the lens of institutional theory. Based on a pragmatic approach, this study has collected data from 455 participants and 21 semi-structured interviews have been conducted. Firstly, it is noted that accounting practices can be traced back to the Mughal regime and subsequently underwent a major development in the British colonial system. Secondly, our results indicate that institutional factors, namely, accounting regulatory framework, political factors, economic factors, cultural factors, and country-specific factors have also played a major role in the development of accounting practices after the creation of Pakistan as a separate state.

Finally, this study suggests that the development of accounting practices has a novel contribution toward the performance of firms. This research thus provides a pathway for policymakers in this country to close the gaps between accounting practices and the policies of the International Accounting Standard Board (IASB). Furthermore, firms can enhance their performance by implementing international accounting standards. This paper helps Pakistan's regulatory institutions such as the SECP (Securities and Exchange Commission of Pakistan) and SBP (State Bank of Pakistan) in the process of developing new policies. Such decisions are related, but not limited to: attracting foreign investments, economic expansion, and international trade. Additionally, it provides a pathway for firms to improve their performance. Ultimately, this research fills the gap concerning international accounting standards by assessing, both empirically and theoretically, the role of various determinants for the formulation of accounting practices and their impact on the performance of firms.

5. METHODOLOGY

5.1 Research Design

A quantitative survey design was adopted in this study. Data was gathered primarily from the practitioner-DisCos to ascertain the regulatory accounting policies and financial management of DisCos. The choice of the method was largely based on the fact that the data will be collected via questionnaires from the selected samples. The survey research method can be generalized and is often reliable, versatile and cost-effective hence making it a good choice for the study (Blackstone, 2018).

5.2 Population and Samples

The population of the study comprises key staff of the Finance and Accounts Department in the eleven (11) electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria. It is worth noting that, these financial officers are distributed across the country because the DisCos are broken down into Regional and Area Offices. Each of the DisCo has a sizeable number of financial officers although the number varies across DisCo. This study adopts a Taro Yamane model as a result the sample is limited to 142 responses. The samples were drawn from the staff of the Finance and Accounts Department of the eleven (11) distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria.

5.3 Research Instrument

The main instrument of data collection was a questionnaire. The independent variables were measured by asking respondents to indicate on a scale of 1 (not effective) to 5 (very effective), the extent to which each item explains the effectiveness of the independent variables in affecting the outcome variables. The independent variables were extracted from the Uniform System of Account-USoA (2014) for regulatory accounting policies. The financial management measurement validated questionnaire adopted by Otoo (2024) was adapted to design financial management items for this study.

5.4 Model specification and measurement of Variables

Nature	Variable	Acronym	Measurement	Source
Independent Variable	Regulatory Accounting Policy	RAP	6 Items	Uniform System of Account (2014)
Dependent Variable	Financial Management	FM	10 Items	Otoo (2024).

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025

Model Specification

Operational Relationship Model - Financial Management = f (Regulatory Accounting Policies)

Econometric Model

$$FM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RAP_i + \varepsilon \quad \text{EQ 1}$$

$$WCM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RAP_i + \varepsilon \quad \text{EQ 2}$$

$$CBM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RAP_i + \varepsilon \quad \text{EQ 3}$$

$$ASM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 RAP_i + \varepsilon \quad \text{EQ 4}$$

Where:

FM= Financial Management

WCM= Working Capital Management

CBM= Capital Budget Management

ASM= Asset Management

RAP=Regulatory Accounting Policies

β_0 = Constant

$\beta_1 - \beta_5$ = Regression Coefficients

ε_i = Error term.

5.5 Model Estimation Technique

The data collected for this study was analysed using partial least square structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) regression analysis. The model is estimated using PLS because **structural equation modeling (SEM)** enables researchers to incorporate unobservable variables measured indirectly by indicator variables. They also facilitate accounting for **measurement errors** in observed variables (Chin, 1998). Data cleansing and screening techniques were applied in order to avoid spurious regression.

6. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Figure 1

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

Model A - Construct Reliability and Validity

Table 6.1

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability (rho_a)	Composite Reliability (rho_c)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
ASM	0.803	0.8090	0.8840	0.7180
CBM	0.852	0.8630	0.9100	0.7710
RAP	0.918	0.9220	0.9370	0.7110
WCM	0.835	0.8410	0.8900	0.6690

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

This study conducted reliability analysis using both Cronbach’s Alpha and composite reliability scores as indicated in table 6.1 above. Both analyses indicated high scores above the 0.700 benchmark. This is an indication that all the measures are internally consistent across measures and that the reliability is good enough for further analysis. According to Cronbach, SchOnemann, and Linn (1971), a higher level of Cronbach’s alpha (CA) between the items means that the items within the construct have the same meaning. Meanwhile, in PLS, internal consistency is measured by composite reliability (CR) as suggested by Chin, (1998). Composite reliability (CR) takes into account indicators that have different loadings. For the evaluation of internal consistency, it is considered satisfactory when the value is ≥ 0.700 (Nunnally, 1994).

The average variance extracted (AVE) tests for both divergent and convergent validity reflect the average communality for each latent factor in a reflective model. This study’s AVE is generally above 0.500 which is considered to be within acceptable limits. According to Chin (1998); and Höck and Ringle (2006), in an adequate model, AVE should be greater than 0.5. It should also be greater than the cross-loadings therefore indicating that factors should explain at least half the variance of their respective indicators.

Table 6.2: Discriminant Validity – Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT)

	ASM	CBM	RAP	WCM
ASM				
CBM	0.881			
RAP	0.796	0.759		
WCM	0.874	0.941	0.766	

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) measures validity by indicating the relationship between heterotrait and monotrait coefficients as shown intable 6.2 above. This study identified indicators across all variables at less than 0.90 except for one. According to Gold et al., (2001) and Teo et al., (2008), a 0.9 cut-off is an indication of the establishment of good discriminant validity. Henseler, Ringle and Sarstedt (2015) also suggested that if the HTMT value is below 0.9, discriminant validity has been established between a given pair of reflective constructs. It is however noted that the validity measures between capital budget management (CBM) and working capital management (WCM) show weak validity as reported by the HTMT matrix, further analysis conducted with the Fornell – Larcker Criterion shows a better output for validity thus ensuring that the validity concerns would not affect the output of the analysis.

Table 6.3: Discriminant Validity - Fornell - Larcker Criterion

	ASM	CBM	RAP	WCM
ASM	0.848			
CBM	0.728	0.878		
RAP	0.686	0.678	0.844	
WCM	0.716	0.792	0.676	0.818

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

Fornell–Larcker criterion establishes discriminant validity with the use of average variance extracted (AVE) as depicted in table 6.3 above. It indicates that, for any latent variable, the square root of the average variance extracted should be higher than the correlation reported with any other latent variable. This suggests that for any latent variable, the variance shared with its block of indicators is greater than the variance it shares with any other latent variable. The Fornell-Larcker criterion displayed in Table 6.3 shows the square root of AVE appears in the diagonal cells and correlations appear below it. Therefore, in absolute value terms, if the top number (which is the square root of AVE) in any factor column is higher than the numbers (correlations) below it, there is discriminant validity.

Test of Hypothesis

Figure II

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

Figure II shows the outcome of the construct coefficient as well as the inner path coefficients depicting the model’s R square on the construct of the various components of the dependent variable. It signifies that across the models, the study’s independent variables account for 45.7% of the changes in working capital management, 45.9% of the changes in capital budget management and 47% of changes in asset management which are all proxies of the dependent variable-financial management. In other words, regulatory accounting policies could account for 45.7% effect on the working capital management, 45.9% on capital budget management and 47% of asset management of electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria while other factors unknown to this study also have their respective impacts on the dependent variable-financial management.

Table 6.4: Model A-Path Coefficient Output

Variables	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
RAP -> ASM	0.6860	0.6870	0.0570	12.0850	0.0000
RAP -> CBM	0.6780	0.6780	0.0480	13.9730	0.0000
RAP -> WCM	0.6760	0.6780	0.0540	12.6230	0.0000

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

Variables	R-Square	R-Square adjusted
ASM	0.4700	0.4660
CBM	0.4590	0.4550
WCM	0.4570	0.4530

Source: Author’s Computation through Smart-PLS Output (2025)

Hypothesis One:

H01: Regulatory accounting policies do not significantly affect the asset management of Discos in Nigeria.

This study found that regulatory accounting policies significantly affect the asset management of electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria. This is depicted by $t=12.0850$; $p<0.05$ as indicated in table 6.4. This implies that the positive relationship depicted in the path coefficient output is statistically significant hence indicating that asset management in DisCos is affected by regulatory accounting policies (RAP).

Hypothesis Two:

H02: Regulatory accounting policies significantly affect the capital budget management of Discos in Nigeria.

This study tested whether regulatory accounting policies significantly affect the capital budget management of DisCos in Nigeria. This is depicted by $t=13.9730$; $p<0.05$ as indicated in table 6.4. This implies that the positive relationship depicted in the path coefficient output is statistically significant hence indicating that capital budget management in DisCos is affected by regulatory accounting policies (RAP).

Hypothesis Three:

H03: Regulatory accounting policies do not significantly affect the working capital management of Discos in Nigeria.

The study submits regulatory accounting policies (RAP) significant effect on the working capital management (WCM) of (DisCos) in Nigeria. This is depicted by $t=12.6230$; $p<0.05$ as indicated in table 6.4. This implies that the positive relationship depicted in the path coefficient output is statistically significant hence indicating that working capital management in distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria is significantly affected by regulatory accounting policies (RAP).

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The effect of regulatory accounting policy on the financial management of electricity distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria is the main objective of the study. Financial management which is the dependent variable is proxied with working capital management (WCM), capital budget management (CBM) and asset management (AM). Regulatory accounting policies were found to have significantly effected all the three components of the financial management of DisCos.

The result of the study provides evidence to support that regulatory accounting policy affects the financial management in DisCos. It noted, in consistence with the studies of Cernius and Birskyte (2020) that the choice of accounting policy, specifically the depreciation period and methods, can significantly impact the accuracy and reliability of financial information in the firm's financial ratios and potentially misleading information for decision making, Jelena Raicevic & Marija Stojiljkovic (2022) established that the attainment of company goals, such as achieving the highest profit, preserving liquidity, and ensuring continuity of operations, is aided by the selection and application of appropriate accounting policies. Nnah (2017) noted that accounting estimates had a significant relationship with financial reporting quality while John and Isamade (2021) study revealed that accounting policies in disclosure of inventories and disclosure of receivables significantly affect return on assets of firms in Nigeria.

Upon further disaggregation of financial management into three components-working capital management, capital budget management, and asset management, it is noted that regulatory accounting policies have positive and significant effect of all the components of financial management. This is in conformity with the studies of Kulwa et.al., (2023) which revealed that working capital management practices and financing management practices have significant positive influence on both financial and organizational performance in a survey carried out on Agro enterprises and Otoo (2024) which indicate that working capital and capital budget management significantly influenced organizational performance.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

The study sought to determine the effect of regulatory accounting policies on financial management of DisCos in Nigeria. For effective analysis, the dependent variable is proxied by working capital management, capital budget management and asset management. The variables were conceptualized to gain better understanding of the concepts. Extant literatures were reviewed and streamlined to establish the intent of the researcher and provide an absolute motive for conducting the study as well as offer more insight on the main objective of the study. The literature review also examined empirical works of experts around the globe in the field of accounting policies and financial management. The interconnectivity of the literature gives a preview and optimism for the furtherance of the research work. A qualitative research methodology was considered most appropriate with questionnaires shared among the eleven (11) DisCos. Taro Yamane (TY) model sampling technique was adopted, and multiple regression analysis was carried out on the questionnaire responses. Precisely, the method of analysis adopted enabled the identification of the outstanding accomplishment of this research.

The study is unique in the sense that although other researchers have attempted research on the related variable, it is the first of its kind in relation to DisCos.

Analysis of the variants established that regulatory accounting policies significantly and positively affect the three components of financial management in the DisCos. The study submits that improvement in the choice and application of appropriate regulatory accounting policies is vital to achievement of effective financial management in DisCos. The conclusions drawn from the findings of this study provide opportunities to make recommendations for concerned stakeholders including the regulators, private investors, management and policy makers. The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC), which is in charge of regulating the NESI should further strengthen its regulatory oversight by enforcing the adaption of the uniform system of accounts USofA, applying and imposing sanctions where necessary for non-compliance as well as incentives such as timely review of OPEX request to encourage continuous compliance and improvement by the DisCos.

Furtherance to strengthening of regulatory accounting policies, is the recommendation for government and private investors to expand the revenue base of the DisCos and increase subvention to them while at the same time expanding its capacity to be able to deliver on its core mandates of electricity distribution in the country. Also, embarking on regulatory tours, trainings and education beyond the shores of Nigeria for both the regulators and the management of DisCOs will expose them to international best practices on electricity regulation and financial management.

References

- 1) Agu et.al., (2024). *Nerc terminates Kaduna Electric's Board over 110bn debt* -. Businessday NG. https://businessday.ng/news/legal-business/article/kaduna-electricity-distribution-company-a-cautionary-tale-for-the-nigerian-electricity-sector/#google_vignette
- 2) Ahmad, M., & Ejaz, T. (2019). Transactional and transformational leadership impact on organizational performance: Evidence from textile sector of Pakistan. *European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences: Proceedings*, 8(2), 97–107.
- 3) Akolo O.A. (2023). *The Nesi Components: exploring the distribution sub-sector* -. Businessday NG. <https://businessday.ng/paywall-free/article/the-nesi-components-exploring-the-distribution-sub-sector/>
- 4) Anderson, J.E. (1975). *Public policy marking*; New Delhi: Praeger Publisher Incorporated.
- 5) ArunKumar et.al., (2019). Advanced metering infrastructure and its role in building smart and sustainable power distribution system: A comprehensive review from India's frame of reference. *International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering* 11(3), 249-268.
- 6) Badulescu, D., Gavrilut, D., Simut, R., Bodog, S. A., Zapodeanu, D., Toca, C. V., & Badulescu, A. (2024). The relationship between sustainable economic growth, R&D expenditures and employment: A regional perspective for the North-West Development Region of Romania. *Sustainability*, 16(2), 760.
- 7) Blackstone, A. (2018). *Principles of sociological inquiry: Qualitative and Quantitative Methods*. Saylor Academy Open Textbooks.
- 8) Businessday (2020). *Business & financial re-engineering of electricity distribution companies* -. <https://businessday.ng/energy/power/article/business-financial-re-engineering-of-electricity-distribution-companies/>

- 9) Capano, G., & Howlett, M. (2024). Calibration and specification in policy practice: Micro-dimensions of policy design. *Policy Design and Practice*, 7(2), 115–128. <https://doi.org/10.1080/25741292.2024.2353929>
- 10) Černius, G., & Birškytė, L. (2020). Financial Information and Management Decisions: Impact of accounting policy on financial indicators of the firm. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 21(1), 48–57. <https://doi.org/10.3846/btp.2020.9959>
- 11) Chin, W.W. 1998. *The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling*. In *Modern methods for business research*, ed. G.A. Marcoulides, 295–336. Mahwah: Erlbaum.
- 12) Cronbach, L., SchOnemann, P., & Linn R.I.R. (1971). *Educational Measurement*: Wiley Online Library
- 13) Devon Dodd J. & Hébert Boyd M. (2000). *Capacity Building: Linking Community Experience to Public Policy*. Population and Public Health Branch. Health Canada: Ottawa
- 14) Erhan, Ica, & Gamureac, M. (2022). *The impact of accounting policies on financial results*. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research.
- 15) Gold, A. H., Malhotra, A., & Segars, A. H. (2001). Knowledge management: An organizational capabilities perspective. *Journal of management information systems*, 18(1), 185-214.
- 16) Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2015). A new criterion for assessing discriminant validity in variance-based structural equation modeling. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 43(1), 115–135. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11747-014-0403-8>
- 17) Höck, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2006). *Strategic networks in the software industry: An empirical analysis of the value continuum*. IFSAM VIIIth World Congress.
- 18) Ibrahim A. (2023). *Nerc Terminates Kaduna Electric's Board Over 110bn Debt* -. *Businessday NG*. <https://businessday.ng/energy/article/nerc-terminates-kaduna-electrics-board-over-n110bn-debt/>
- 19) Kose, M. A., Sugawara, N., & Terrones, M. E. (2020). *Global recessions*. World Bank working paper.
- 20) Lawuyi, R. (2022). *Corporate Governance Compliance and Enforcement in Nigeria*. Available at SSRN 4107906.
- 21) Manghani, K. (2011). Quality assurance: Importance of systems and standard operating procedures. *Perspectives in clinical research*, 2(1), 34-37.
- 22) Matriano M.T., & Nasser J.K, (2022). The impact of internal control systems on the quality of financial reports. *Global Scientific Journals*, 10(6), 1584-1597.
- 23) Mazikana, A. T. (2021). The impact of debt financing on financial performance of mining firms in Harare, Zimbabwe. Zimbabwe. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3973025>
- 24) Nangih, E., Wali, S. C., & Anyanwu, P. O. (2021). Accounting policies, management judgements and financial reporting quality of small and medium enterprises in Nigeria: A survey. *International Journal of Finance Research*. 2(2). 58-70. DOI. <https://doi.org/10.47747/ijfr.v2i2.326>.
- 25) Nerc. (2014). *Uniform system of accounts (USOA) guidelines 2014*. <https://nerc.gov.ng/index.php/library/documents/func-startdown/631/>
- 26) Nnodim O. (2024). *Nerc dissolves Kaduna DisCo Board Over 110bn Debt* -. *Punch.NG*. <https://punchng.com/nerc-dissolves-kaduna-disco-board-over-n110bn-debt/>
- 27) Odo, J., & Isamade, A. B. (2021). Implications Of Accounting Policies on Firm Performance in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences*, 10(9), 19-37. ISSN 2278-6236

- 28) Okolie A. O. & Omoregie A.E.N. (2014). Accounting Policies and Comparability of Companies' Financial Reports in Nigeria. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 16(1), 10-16.
- 29) Olaniyi J.O. (1998) *Foundations of public policy analysis*: Ibadan, Sunad Publishers Limited.
- 30) Olatunji, T.E (2013). The impact of accounting system on the performance of small and medium scale enterprises in Nigeria – A survey of SME's In Oyo State-Nigeria. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*. 2(9), 13-17.
- 31) Otoo F.N. K., Kaur M., & Rather N.A. (2023). Evaluating the impact of internal control systems on organizational effectiveness. *LBS Journal of Management & Research*, 21(1), 135-154. Published by Emerald Publishing Limited. DOI 10.1108/LBSJMR-11-2022-0078
- 32) Otoyebi (2023). The Role of Nigeria's Financial Reporting Council Under the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria Act, 2011. <https://omaplex.com.ng/the-role-of-nigerias-financial-reporting-council-under-the-financial-reporting-council-of-nigeria-act-2011/>
- 33) Pandey (2015). *Financial Management*. Vikas Publishing House PVT Ltd, India, 11th Edition, ISBN: 978-93259-8229-1
- 34) Pandey, K. D., & Sahu, T. N. (2019). Debt financing, agency cost and firm performance: Evidence from India. *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*, 23(3), 267–274. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0972262919859203>
- 35) Raicevic J. & Stojiljkovic M., (2022). The Importance of Choosing and Applying Accounting Policies in the Corporate Management System. *FINIZ 2022-Business Resilience in a Changing World*, 32-38. DOI: 10.15308/finiz-2022-32-38.
- 36) Rossouw, J. (2010). Empirical results of the accounting policies chosen by South African listed companies. *Meditari Accountancy Research*, 18(2), 38–56. <https://doi.org/10.1108/10222529201000009>
- 37) Sapru, R. K (2009). *Administrative Theories and Management Through*; New Delhi. PHI Learning Private Limited.
- 38) Sunday E.S. (2023). *Nerc to revoke Kaduna DisCo's Licence over N51bn Debt* -. Daily Trust NG. <https://dailytrust.com/nerc-to-revoke-kaduna-discos-licence-over-n51bn-debt/>
- 39) Torjman, S. (2005). *What is Policy?* Ottawa: Caledon Institute of Social Policy, September. www.caledoninst.org
- 40) USAID, (2019). *Nigeria Power Sector Program Disco Appraisal*: Eko Electricity Distribution Company.
- 41) Uwanaka C., (2022). *Strategic management and consolidation for Nigeria's electricity industry*-. The Cable.NG. <https://www.thecable.ng/strategic-management-and-consolidation-for-nigerias-electricity-industry/>
- 42) World Bank (2021). *Nigeria Distribution Sector Recovery Program (2021)*. The World Bank.
- 43) Ziorklui, J. E. K., Ampofo, F. O., Nyonyoh, N., & Antwi, B. O. (2024). Effectiveness of internal controls mechanisms in preventing and detecting fraud. *Finance & Accounting Research Journal*, 6(7), 1259-1274.